

Welcome to the DATAMITE Newsletter

Our motto: Unleashing the Monetisation Potential of Data.

Driving Data Innovation: Progress and future plans for DATAMITE pilots

The **DATAMITE** project is steadily progressing through its six innovative pilots, each addressing unique data management challenges and demonstrating DATAMITE's potential for innovation in data sharing, governance and quality assessment. With milestones set through 2025, these **pilots will strengthen the DATAMITE framework's** ability to address diverse sectoral challenges and provide sustainable, scalable solutions for data sharing and management.

Here is an **overview of the progress and upcoming milestones** for each of these pilot.

[Read the full article](#)

DATAMITE plenary meeting in Aachen

From 26 to 28 November, the **DATAMITE consortium met in Aachen for its second – and last – plenary meeting of 2024**. As at the previous plenary meeting in Poznan, the agenda was divided into a first day of CodeCamp with the developers involved in the project, followed by two days with the whole consortium, where each work package had its moment in the spotlight with presentations and/or workshops.

In addition to three intense days of work, the DATAMITE consortium enjoyed a guided tour of the Aachen Christmas Market and a visit to the [Demonstration Factory](#), which is a central component of the Smart Logistics Cluster on the RWTH Aachen campus, thanks to the colleagues from [FIR RWTH Aachen University](#), who hosted this plenary meeting.

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International events

DATAMITE at the first Gaia-X Hub Spain Data Space Summit

The first [Gaia-X Hub Spain](#) Data Space Summit (“[Primera cumbre de espacios datos](#)“, as it is called in Spanish) took place in Madrid on 3 and 4 December. The event brought together prominent leaders of national initiatives, government representatives and **European project managers in the field of Data Spaces**, Technology and Artificial Intelligence.

DATAMITE, as a European project focused on the monetisation of data and data spaces, coordinated by a Spanish entity ([ITI](#)), did not miss the event.

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DATAMITE at InfoCom World 2024

The [26th InfoCom World Conference](#) was held in Athens on 12 November 2024 under the theme ‘Digital Greece: Time to take the leap’. The thematic sections of the conference covered key topics such as: private networks, artificial intelligence, data centres, e-government, smart cities and digital projects, with an emphasis on the practical application and benefits of new technologies, bringing together key speakers from Greece and abroad. **DATAMITE was present at InfoCom 2024 in two ways:** Participating in a session and at the OTE booth.

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DATAMITE attends the AI Data, Robotics Forum 2024

DATAMITE's paper wins an award at ICCBDC 2024

DATAMITE attends the AI Data, Robotics Forum 2024

The second edition of the [AI, Data and Robotics Forum \(ADRF\)](#) took place on 4 and 5 November in Eindhoven, the Netherlands. Under the theme 'European Sovereignty in AI, Data and Robotics', the programme featured visionary keynotes and thought-provoking panels, as well as a series of parallel sessions on key industrial and societal issues.

DATAMITE did not miss the opportunity to participate. The project was a **Silver Sponsor of ADRF 2024** and the project coordinator, Santiago Cáceres ([ITI](#)), travelled to Eindhoven to **present DATAMITE at the poster exhibition**

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DATAMITE presents a paper at ICCBDC 2024

DATAMITE presented the paper called '[Purity: a New Dimension for Measuring Data Centralization Quality](#)' at the International Conference on Cloud and Big data ([ICCBDC](#)) 2024, held at Oxford University from 15 to 17 August. Written by researchers from [Tecnalia](#), partner of DATAMITE, and from [Deusto Institute of Technology](#), it introduced a new dimension of data quality called 'Purity'.

As part of the outstanding work carried out by the researchers and their presentation at the ICCBDC, **they were awarded the Excellent Oral Presentation Award at the conference.**

[Discover more](#)

The DATAMITE team wishes you a happy holiday season and a very happy new year 🎆!

Thank you very much for joining us this year. We are excited to see where 2025 takes us, always working as a team to achieve our main goal: to build a modular, open source, multi-domain framework to improve data monetisation.

🎆 HAPPY 2025 🎆

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